

Physico-Chemical Properties of Solid Catalysts: Studies on Thermal Analysis, Infrared and X-ray Diffraction of Ceric Molybdate

P. K. BHATTACHARYA and S. K. BHATTACHARYYA*

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221005.

Manuscript received 4 September 1975, revised 26 December 1975, accepted 5 April 1976.

Thermal analysis of ceric molybdate, $Ce(MoO_4)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ have been studied by DTA and TG techniques and the different transition products obtained have been characterised by Infrared spectroscopic and X-ray diffraction methods.

DTA thermogram shows three endothermic peaks at 170° , 500° and 998° respectively. The TG, Infrared and X-ray diffraction results indicate that the first endothermic peak at 170° is due to complete dehydration of the ceric molybdate, the second peak at 500° results in the decomposition of the molybdate to CeO_2 , MoO_3 and other polyoxides of Mo and the third one at 998° is due to melting.

THE importance of thermal analyses to the study of physico-chemical properties of solid catalysts has well been established by Bhattacharyya. A number of papers have been published and the important findings have been summarized recently in the two reviews^{1,2}.

Ceric molybdate is known to be an oxidation catalyst for the oxidation of toluene to benzaldehyde^{3,4}. The literature survey reveals that very little work has been done on this catalyst. Brixner *et al.*⁵ have studied the structure of the catalyst by X-ray and found it to be triclinic. No attempt, however, has been made yet to study the physico-chemical properties of ceric molybdate in details, when it is thermally treated.

In the present paper results of our detailed investigations on the thermal characteristics of ceric molybdate by DTA, TG, Infrared spectroscopic and X-ray diffraction methods have been presented.

Experimental

Preparation of ceric molybdate: A solution containing 3.2 g. ammonium molybdate in 250 ml. water was added to a solution of 10 g. of ammonium ceric nitrate in one litre of water. The pH was adjusted to 1.45 and the solution was heated at 45° . The resulting yellow precipitate was filtered, dried and ground to 100μ .⁶ All the reagents used were of AnalaR quality.

Chemical analysis

Molybdenum: Molybdenum(VI) was separated from ceric molybdate as molybdenum sulphide by passing H_2S . MoO_3 was then estimated by burning

the sulphide formed. Cerium (Ce^{IV}) was then determined volumetrically. Cerium ion was first reduced to cerous ion by ferrous ammonium sulphate and the excess of ferrous ion titrated with potassium permanganate solution. Water was estimated by the absorption of water in anhydrous magnesium perchlorate using Coleman Carbon-Hydrogen Analyser. The catalyst was subjected to the usual test of nitrogen using Nitrogen Analyser for the detection of ammonia. However, no ammonia was detected.

Instrumentation and procedure

Differential thermal analysis (DTA): Differential thermal analysis of ceric molybdate was conducted in air atmosphere using a manually operated unit. Details of experimental set up have been reported earlier⁷.

Thermogravimetric analysis: Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out by Stanton Mass Flow Thermobalance, Model MFH-5 with programmed heating rate 6.5° min. in air atmosphere.

X-ray diffraction: The X-ray diffraction patterns of ceric molybdate heated at various temperatures (350° , 525° and 1000°) were obtained using a Philips Diffractometer with nickel filtered $CuK\alpha$ radiation. Time of exposure for each of the sample was 6 hr at 50 kV and 16 mA.

Infrared spectroscopy: The infrared absorption spectra of the ceric molybdate samples were taken using Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometers (model 257 and 621) by nujol technique. The spectrum was scanned in the region $4000-625\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Surface area measurement: Surface area of the catalyst heated to different temperatures have been

measured by B.E.T. technique. Helium was used for the measurement of dead space and nitrogen as adsorbent.

intact even after dehydration. At 525° the spectrum obtained was entirely different from those observed

Results and Discussion

The composition and results of thermal analysis of cerium molybdate are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1. RESULTS OF THERMAL ANALYSIS OF CERIUM MOLYBDATE

Composition	Formula	Endo-thermic peak temp °C	Range of temp. °C	% weight loss
Ce—27.3%	Ce(MoO ₄) ₂ 3H ₂ O	170	50-350	10.8 upto 350°C
Mo—37.25%		500	450-525	2.1 within 450-500°C
H ₂ O—10.7%		998	960-1010	Total loss = 13.9%

The thermograms of cerium molybdate are shown in Fig. 1. The DTA curve shows three endothermic peaks at 170° (range 50°-350°), 500° (range 450°-525°) and 998° (range 960°-1010°). The thermogram shows no significant changes within the temperature range 625°-960°. The TG curve registers a two step weight-loss, from the room temperature upto about 350° (10.8%) and from 450° to 500° (2.9%). It appears from the TG curve that the dehydration proceeds through a single step reaction and the catalyst is completely dehydrated at 350° (weight-loss corresponds to the removal of three molecules of water). The small weight-loss of 2.9% at 450° to 500° might be due to the decomposition of part of MoO₃ for the formation of polymolybdates.

The IR spectra of cerium molybdate sample heated at different temperatures exhibits some interesting features. The original sample showed a broad band at 1000-750 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 2) which can be attributed to Mo-O stretching; bands at 3400 and 1620 cm⁻¹ are characteristics of O-H stretching and H-O-H bending and a band at 1160 cm⁻¹ due to M-O-H bending motion. However, at 350° the sample appeared to be completely free from water as revealed by the

FIG 1 DTA AND TG OF CERIUM MOLYBDATE.

earlier. Significant bands appeared at 930, 870 and 780 cm⁻¹, which indicate that at this temperature the catalyst has undergone marked changes. At 1000°, the bands at 930, 870 and 780 cm⁻¹ remained almost unchanged (Fig. 2a).

The X-ray diffraction pattern of ceric molybdate at 350° showed some very weak lines whose d-values could not be identified with any of the decomposition products like, CeO₂, MoO₃ etc. As indicated by TG and IR results and from the presence of very weak lines in the X-ray pattern it may be concluded that the ceric molybdate was transformed to highly dehydrated and amorphous state. At 525° some strong, medium strong and medium lines appeared

FIG 2 Infrared Spectra of Ceric Molybdate

complete absence of all the bands characteristics of water. The band at 1000-750 cm⁻¹ remained whose d-values (3.85, 3.69, 3.11, 3.05, 2.70, 2.30, 1.91, 1.778 and 1.63 Å) are identical with those

